

THE EFFECT OF CYBER-LOAFING ON EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE: A CASE OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTES (HEI) IN KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA

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ABSTRACT

The use of Internet hailed as a technological instrument which led the expansion of significant opportunities for organizations and the improvement of workers' productivity. Internet not only changed the base of businesses to be conducted but it also improved the nature of work. Internet has many benefits, for instance reducing costs, limiting product cycle time, facilitate information access, and promoting products and services more efficiently, internet has also adverse effects on the performance of workers in different organisations that include workers' anxieties about privacy, productivity loss, and institutional liability results from workers' outbound and inbound Internet activities. The current study was conducted to explore the effect of Cyber-loafing on employees' performance: a case of Higher Education Institutes (HEI) in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The objectives of the study were to examine the effect of Cyber-loafing on the job performance of the employees of universities and to compare the effects of Cyber-loafing on the performance of employees of private and Public Sector Universities. Primary data collected from the employees of 08 different universities including 04 public and 04 private universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Total 353 questionnaires regarding Cyber-loafing are developed for 353 employees and descriptive statistical techniques and quantitative approach was applied. The findings of this study concluded statistically significant inverse relationship between cyber-loafing activities and employees' performance in both private and public universities. The magnitude -0.391 of employees' performance explains that employees performance is inversely affect by 39.1% because of cyber-loafing activities and overall value of Cronbach's alpha is $.857$ which indicates a high reliability. This study recommended high control over sources of cyber-loafing and development of software to block such sites like YouTube, Facebook and other social websites as well as apps related to entertainment and cyber-loafing, implementations of rules and regulations of punishment on using such types websites and apps during duty hours and vigilant check is necessary to control the cyber-loafing in the universities/institutes/ organizations.

INTRODUCTION

The use of Internet hailed as a technological instrument which led the expansion of significant opportunities for organizations and the improvement of workers' productivity. Internet not only changed the base of businesses to be conducted but it also improved the nature of work.

Internet has many benefits, for instance reducing costs, limiting product cycle time, facilitate information access, and promoting products and services more efficiently, internet has also adverse effects on the performance of workers in different organisations that include workers' anxieties

about privacy, productivity loss, and institutional liability results from workers' outbound and inbound Internet activities

Cyber-loafing is a new phenomenon that arise with the evolution of I.T. in the early 19th century no one was aware of cyber-loafing but after the extension of I.T in 1990's cyber-loafing activities starts and now it present almost all worker are engaged in some type of cyber-loafing. Cyber-loafing also known as cyberslacking is workers' non-work use of organization Internet facilities by visiting social sites and checking personal email while working (Lim, 2002). Some type of cyber-loafing are considered relatively harmless for organizations, particularly if limited in duration and usage (e.g., receiving and sending of private email or checking news headlines). While other forms of cyber-loafing like online shopping and visiting social sites and online gambling etc are harmful and problematic for organization either as they are time intense and hence reduce worker's productivity.

cyber loafing behaviour has positive and significant influence of job stress, there is a positive and significant influence of job boredom on cyber loafing behaviour, cyber loafing behaviour negative and significant influence of on employee performance, there is a significant influence between cyber loafing behaviour mediating stress on employee performance whereas there is no significant influence between cyber loafing behaviour mediating job boredom on employee performance Kamila, & Muafi. (2023) Naoreen, et al. (2023) Examined the impact of workplace ostracism on stress and work engagement among university teachers Workplace ostracism was found to have a detrimental effect on stress levels and work engagement

There are many possible reasons why employees cyber loaf. Previous research has examined the factors that cause this behaviour, including research by: (Schott and Fischer 2023) who explained that boredom in employees can lead to cyber loafing, where the boredom arises due to relatively monotonous work and too much workload. Based on (Koay and Soh 2018), employees who are bored with their work tend to do cyber loafing as a suggestion to seek entertainment. (Adiba, Kadiyono, and Hanami 2021) mentioning another factor in cyberloafing is to relieve fatigue or stress. Several studies according to (Anandarajan and Simmers 2005)

mentioned the positive impacts of cyber loafing, including reduced work stress and increased work productivity. (Tsai 2023); (Zhong et al. 2022); (Rahman, Kistyanto, and Surjanti 2022) cyberloafing can create inspiration and creativity

As at present Internet access facilities at work place are more common for workers, so their frequency to use Internet for social sites, entertainment and additional non-work purposes at office. According to (Greengard, 2002) 56% of workers were use Internet for private purpose while in 2003 this statistics increased to 59% (Griffiths, 2003) and in 2005 more than 75/% of the employees spent time on unproductive internet usage (Malachowski, 2005). According to (Beldona, Mills, Hu, & Clay 2001 and Davis & Greenfield, 2002) the per hour unproductive internet use increased from 2.5 hours per day to 3 hours per day in 2001 to 2003.

There are various definitions and approaches for non-work related practice in public and private organizations. Alterations in approaches resulted in comprehensive and unpredictable use of expressions and definitions (Weatherbee, 2010). Several concepts and expressions were used to explore the phenomenon, containing non work related use, cyber-loafing, cyber budging and cyber slacking, on-line loafing, internet deviation, problematical internet use, private web practice at work, internet addiction and internet exploitation (Bryne and Kim, 2011). These terms vary in their gradations according to the explanations and results of engagement in cyber-loafing followed by the frequency of interactivity. Yet, amongst these scholars, there are also no agreement in defining the features of these gradations. The collective thread among these expressions is that all these explains unproductive usage of the Internet at office (Ugrin *et al*, 2008).

Most common terms used in previous research are cyber-loafing, non-work-related and cyber-slacking. The words cyber-loafing and cyber-slacking are used to define voluntary actions of workers consuming their firms' Internet facilities for non-work-related dedications during office timing (Lim 2002). Cyber-slacking has defined as wastage of time in unproductive internet activities during working hours. It has also called cyber-slouching (Jessup and Urbaczewski 2002), whereas (Guthrie and Gray 1996) termed it as junk computing and (Lim, 2002) as cyber-loafing and (Lee *et al* 2005)

used non-work related term. Shortly, somewhat that workers waste time on Internet during working hours is called cyber-slacking or cyber-loafing (Ugrin *et al* 2008). Job searching, receiving and sending personal e-mail, surfing, online shopping, watching news, you tube and downloading non work related objects are some type of cyber-loafing that are found more prevalent at work place (Weatherbee, 2010)

Numerous researchers try to highlight the positive effect of cyber-loafing. Lim and Chen study showed positive effect of cyber-loafing on individuals work performance (Lim & Chen, 2012). Matthew Eastin stated that many scholars usually conceptualize cyber-loafing as just one additional sort of predictable deviant behaviour at work, others reflect this activity to be harmless and even productive” (Glynn, Griffiths and Eastin 2007). Eastin concluded that the earlier works in research that defined cyber-loafing beneath deviance was not definite in respects to the adverse effects of cyber-loafing. Research have made cases for both negative and positive effects of cyber-loafing because cyber-loafing is a common term for a kind of loafing. There exists many types of cyber-loafing activities that vary in apparent seriousness and their influence on employees’ performance are vary. Christine stressed that some sorts of cyber-loafing are constructive where as others might be destructive (Blanchard & Henle, 2008) another study conducted by J.Q. Chen showed that even non work-related e-mailing can affect employ performance but internet surfing may be actually a positive activity (Schings, 2014).

Causation of Cyber-loafing:

The expansion of internet facilities has endorsed cyber-loafing to occur, but other situations can encourage and discourage the use of cyber-loafing. As technology has continuous to increase the extent of devices accessible to employees the capability and expectation of work at home increased. The Lim and Teo (2005) study revealed that working adults consumed an average of 4.6 hours/ week at home on professional activities where as they spent an average of 3.3 hours/week using organizational Internet for personal activities. Another research showed still more time consumed at home office work activities are 5.9 hours/week (Lim & Teo 2005). This explains that although workers may choose to cyber-loaf at

office but they are spend even additional time on office work at home.

Effects of cyber-loafing go afar outer forces for instance working hours. Besides this external Cumulative studies showed that personal traits has powerful influence on explaining of multitude on individual’s behaviour and attitudes at workplac (Jia, & Karau, 2013). One of these behaviours at workplace is cyber-loafing. Jia, and Karau explored the influence of personality, especially the Big Five, on worker’s cyber-loafing behaviours. These are the five traits that state to human behaviour. Earlier research on this revealed that The Big Five traits are the determinant of individual internet usage by college and university student (Jia, & Karau, 2013). This indicate that the high chance of cyber-loafing activities. It is essential to note Jia, , and Karau founding to consider worker’s gender and age as these are significantly associated to cyber-loafing, the results of (Jia, & Karau, 2013) concluded that younger male employees were more probable engaged in cyber-loafing than older and female employees. Age and Gender are inner influences on persons that are engaged in cyber-loafing. Previous studies has mostly supported the impression that men are more expected to cyber-loaf than women for various different causes. One reason has that simple because men were use internet more than women (Zhang, 2004). (Schings, 2014) suggested that males were more assertive in consuming internet because it’s a source entertainment for their own while females were not as much of confident that male and would have adverse attitude to cyber-loafing

There is common consensus on the association of age and Cyber-some studies explored inverse relationship between age and cyber-loafing while other concluded positive correlation between them. (Restubog, *et al.*, 2011) find significantly direct relationship between cyber-loafing and age their study concluded that Younger persons are typically more engaged in cyberloafing than elder people. This is attributed because of a multitude of causes with one of key reason is being understanding with internet technology. Yet there are definite situations where age has truly been revealed positively correlated to cyber-loafing. One study concluded that older workers engaged more in cyber-loafing as compared to younger worker (Restubog, *et al*, 2011).

Types of Cyber-loafing Activities:

Certain situations were supposed to encourage cyber-loafing activities. There are various different activities which fall in the type of cyber-loafing that can be organized based on their comparative seriousness and occurrence. Lim and Teo conducted various surveys requesting groups of employed adults on their awareness of cyber-loafing actions. They establish that the alleged seriousness and prevalence of activities were inversely associated (Lim & Teo, 2005). Surfing several types of sites such as sports, entertainment and news were the most prevailing activities and assessed among the least severe. Private email practice was stated as rarer serious with getting email being the most prevailing and sending e-mail the least. Looking for employment, shopping online and playing games were the smallest prevalence activities (Lim & Chen, 2012 and Lim & Teo, 2005). The opposite association between prevalence and seriousness suggested that workers are more probable to explain the activities which are less severe. Existing literature focused on identification and types of cyber-loafing. Lim (2002) and Rajah (2011) define Cyber-loafing in two categories that are E-mailing and slacking the web. They define slacking as reading news on web, visiting social sites and online shopping. Blao *et al* (2003) extend Lim's definition and include online games and chatting with other people by using office internet facilities they analyzed data for Lim's factors like slacking and e-mailing and added new factors online chat and shopping. The results suggest that all workers involve in online chatting while 70% of employees were engaged in online shopping. . Ramayah (2010) established other type of Cyber-loafing and divided it in four categories. The first category was introduced as personal communications that include social activities like facebook, whatsapp, twitter and booger etc, the second category was named as access to personal information that consist of searching information like visiting news site or other informative site, activities like downloading music, or watching live match or highlights, playing games etc are categorized as personal downloads or Leisure activity. The fourth activity was named personal e-commerce which is consisting of online shopping. Mahantankon *et al* identify three deficiencies in Lim's definition and categorized them as E-commerce, personal communication and information search and the

fourth category was developed by Henel and Blanchard in 2008 their study concluded that irrespective of other types of cyber-loafing behaviour visiting adults site are more serious and alarming

Antecedents of Cyber-loafing:

In previous studies antecedents of cyber-loafing are studied in three main categories i,e Personal, organizational and work

Personal Factors

Personal traits means a person characteristics that predict its behavior towards internet use Personal traits such as energetic approach to social world, activity, sociability, boldness and positive approach and internet facility are the personal determinants of cyber-loafing (Landers and Lounsbury 2006). The negative association between internet use and agreeableness was studied by Philips and Wyatt (2005) they demonstrated opposed interpersonal setting between agreeableness and internet usage. They also concluded inverse relationship between personality and level of internet, persons that are more reliable and organized has lower level of interruption in internet use but in regard extraversion they found positive correlation between cyber-loafing and extraversion.

Work Factors

Job requirements: cyber-loafing behavior studies showed that when workers are confronting with low job demands, the probability of engaging in cyber-loafing is more than high work demands. This is cause because of spare time available to employees in office time. When workers did not have sufficient work, they are engage in cyber-loafing behavior to surpass the time. Henle and Blanchard (2003) also concluded that high job requirements result in decrease the opportunity of cyber-loafing. Both edges of job demand boost cyber-loafing. Thus, Blanchard and Henle suggested finding a intensity of work for workforce that results in minimum cyber-loafing (Kidwell, 2010).

Role conflict has defined as incompatible requirements at organizations. These consist of conflicts in job duties and managerial polices, followed by conflicts between an worker's personal ethics and work responsibilities. Blancard and Henle argued that these factors are

significant deterrents of cyber-loafing. Thus, workers who practice a sharp role of conflict in workplace were more likely to Cyber-loafing (Freimark, 2012).

Organizational Factors

Organizational strategies: organizational antecedents are consider because of its important in policy effectiveness such as whether the policy has negatively or positively affect cyber-loafing. Policies which integrated of politics that demonstrate the use of Internet (Caplan, 2002) studies concluded that a useful and effective policy concerning the exercise of Internet by workers at work place is an efficient technique to overcome this incident.

Executive justice: literature suggested that if workers suffer unfair treatment by organizations, they practice feelings of irritation, anger and are more expected to hunt for revenge against institute. Finding of these Studies showed that workers hunt to connect in deviant behaviors and work less. This type of cyber-loafing is because of technology offer safe atmosphere for such persons (Venkatraman, 2008).

RESEARCH DESIGN

The current study is following the quantitative approach of methodology, a survey method is espoused in conducting this research where for data collection survey questionnaires were filled from the employees of 08 different universities including public universities and private universities of Peshawar region. For measuring the data, 5-point Likert scale which is ranging from ‘Strongly Disagree’ to ‘Strongly Agree’. The collected were analysed through statistical tools.

POPULATION

The total population of the current study was 3000 employees from 08 different universities including public universities and private universities of the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province.

SAMPLE SIZE

The researcher of this study used a random sampling method for the data collection; as per Cochran Formula total number of 353 employees out of 3000 was selected for the purpose to fill the questionnaires.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

To collect the data from the employees of 08 different universities including public and private universities of Peshawar region, a questionnaire was developed in such a way that identified those factors of Cyber loafing which affect the performance of the employees.

DATA COLLECTION METHODS

In this research study, the basic source of collecting data is primary data which were collected from the employees of 08 different universities including public and private universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The method used in this research study is a 5-point Likert scale which is ranging from ‘Strongly Disagree’ to ‘Strongly Agree’. The response ratio of the respondents was 100% because all of the 353 employees filled the questionnaires.

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

For the research study, the quantitative analyses were used because of the numeric nature of data, which were collected from the respondents. The purpose of the analyses was to know the basic facts, preferences and trends of employees. The data which were collected from the respondents were converted to MS EXCEL for statistical measurement.

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

Demographic Analysis

The feature which is relating to statistical and structure characteristics of the people, the researcher has used the SPSS V21 to analyze the data.

Table. 1
Gender of the employee

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid male	231	65.4	65.4	65.4
female	122	34.6	34.6	100.0
Total	353	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 shows that there were total 231 male respondents out of 353 which is 65% of the total while total female respondents were 122 out of 353 which is 35% of the total.

Table. 2
Age of the employee

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18 to 27 years	117	33.1	33.1	33.1
28 to 37 years	131	37.1	37.1	70.3
38 to 47 years	73	20.7	20.7	90.9
48 to 58 years	32	9.1	9.1	100.0
Total	353	100.0	100.0	

As shown in table 2 above, in this research study the employees who are in between 28 to 37 years old are more in numbers who are 131 in numbers and 37% of the total samples, while people who are from 18 to 27 years old are second large population of the total samples who are 117 in

numbers and 33%. People who are among 38 to 47 years old are 73 in numbers and 21 % of the total samples who are third in number of the samples. And people who are from 48 to 58 years old are 32 in numbers and 9% of the total.

Table 3
Discipline/ Department of the Employee

Departments	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Accounting	39	11.0	11.0	11.0
Biological science	61	17.3	17.3	28.3
Social science	40	11.3	11.3	39.7
Banking & Finance	44	12.5	12.5	52.1
Creative & Design	51	14.4	14.4	66.6
Engineering	36	10.2	10.2	76.8
Human Resources	38	10.8	10.8	87.5
IT & Computer Sci	19	5.4	5.4	92.9
Management sciences	25	7.1	7.1	100.0
Total	353	100.0	100.0	

As shown in table 3 in this study, employees of 08 different universities including public and private sectors, people who were belonged to account section were 39 in numbers out of 353 which is 11%. Employees who were belonged to Biological sciences department were 61 in numbers out of 353 which is 17%. Employees who were belonged to Social Sciences department were 40 in numbers out of the total samples which is 11%. Employees who were belonged to Banking and Finance

department were 44 in numbers out of 353 which is 13%. Employees who were belonged to Creative and Design department were 51 in numbers out of 353 which is 14%. Employees who were belonged to human resource department were 38 in numbers which is 11%. Employees who were belonged to IT and computer science department were 19 in numbers which is 5%. Employees who were from management sciences department were 25 in number out of 353 which is 7%.

Table 4
Frequency of time spent on internet use

Time to internet	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-1 hours	44	12.5	12.5	12.5
1-2 hours	101	28.6	28.6	41.1
2-3 hours	90	25.5	25.5	66.6
3-4 hours	46	13.0	13.0	79.6
4-5 hours	44	12.5	12.5	92.1
5-6 hours	12	3.4	3.4	95.5
6-7 hours	16	4.5	4.5	100.0
Total	353	100.0	100.0	

In the table 4, it is shown that 44 employees out of 353 are using internet from 0 to 1 hour during their duty hours which is 12%. Total number of 101 employees out of 353 are using internet during their duty hours from 1 to 2 hours which is 29% of the total sample. People who are using internet from 2 to 3 hours are 90 in numbers of the total 353 which is 26%. Employees who are using internet 3 to 4 hours are 46 in number and 13% of the total samples. Those employees who are using internet 4 to 5 hours during duty timing are 44 in numbers and 13% of the total samples. The employees who are using internet from 5 to 6 hours are 12 in numbers and 3% of the total

samples. Those employees who are using internet 6 to 7 hours are 16 in numbers and 4% of the total samples.

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

Reliability Statistics (Cyberloafing)

For current study reliability analysis was conducted through cronbach's alpha was calculated the acceptable value alpha is 0.7. In this part of the analysis, the results indicates that the questionnaire is how much reliable. The table 5 below shows that the reliability of Cyber loafing is .741 which shows that the data is highly reliable.

Table 5.
Reliability Statistics (CYBERLOAFING)

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.741	12

RELIABILITY STATISTICS (EMPLOYEES PERFORMANCE)

The value of cronbach 's alpha for employees performance is .794 which is again above the

threshold value of .794 so the questionnaire for the employees performance is also reliable. As shown in table 6.

Table 6.
Reliability Statistics (Employees Performance)

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.794	11

RELIABILITY STATISTICS (OVERALL SCALE)

For overall scale the value of cronbach's alpha is calculated and found .857 which is show over all reliability of the scale.

Reliability Statistics (Overall Scale)

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.857	23

CORRELATIONS

Correlation was conducted to find the association between variables Pearson correlation analysis was

conducted which generated the result shown in the table 7

**Table 7.
 Correlations**

		CYBERLOAFING	EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE
CYBERLOAFING	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	353	
EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE	Pearson Correlation	-.391**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	353	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The value of correlation between Cyberloafing and employees performance is -.391** which shows that they exist negative highly significant and moderate association between Cyberloafing and employees performance.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

To test the hypothesis of current study regression analysis was conducted using SPSS V21. The result is shown in table 8

**Table 8
 Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.391 ^a	.153	.151		.9238

a. Predictors: (Constant), CYBERLOAFING

The value of R Square is 0.153 which shows that 15.3% variation in employees' performance is accumulated due to Cyberloafing.

ANOVA Analysis

ANOVA Table

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	54.099	1	54.099	63.390	.000 ^b
Residual	299.555	351	.853		
Total	353.654	352			

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), CYBERLOAFING

The F statistics (63.3) and significance level of .000 shows the fitness of overall model of the current study.

COEFFICIENT OF REGRESSION

The coefficient regression analysis is used to check the association between variables. This analysis also defines if one unit increases in independent variable then how much this brings change in independent variable.

Table 5.5.1

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4.947	.222		22.245	.000
CYBERLOAFING	-.632	.079	-.391	-7.962	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE

The coefficient table shows that there is negative relationship between Cyber loafing and employees performance. One unit increase in Cyber loafing will result in 0.391 units decrease in employees' performance.

Cyber loafing has a significant negative effect on the job performance of employees in HEI. For this research study the primary data is collected from the employees of 08 different universities including 04 public and 04 private universities from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Total population of this study is 3000 and the sample size as per Cochran formula is 353. Total 353 questionnaires regarding Cyber loafing are developed for 353 employees. The collected data was further analysed through statistical tools by using SPSS V20 software.

CONCLUSIONS AND FINDINGS

Conclusions

The current study was conducted just to explore the effect of Cyber loafing on employees' performance: a case of Higher Education Institutes (HEI) in Peshawar region. The objectives of the study were (1) to examine the effect of Cyberloafing on the job performance of the employees of universities. (2) Compare the effects of Cyber loafing on the performance of employees of private and Public Sector Universities. The hypothesis of the study is, H1

Findings

For this research study data was collected from the employees of 08 universities including 04 public universities and 04 private universities of Peshawar region. All of the 353 respondents were

responded. In this study the researcher used statistical tools for testing the theoretical framework. As shown in the tables above, such as table 4.5.6, table 4.7.6, table 4.7, and table 4.8 that independent (cyber loafing) and dependent variable (employees' performance) have negative and significant relationship with each other. As shown in the table 4.7.6 the value of R Square is 0.153 which shows that 15.3% variation in employees' performance (dependent variable) is accumulated due to Cyber loafing (independent variable). In the table above 4.8, the beta value is -.391 and sig value is .000 that shows 1 unit change in cyber loafing acquires -.391 units change in

employees performance which shows a negative but a significant relationship with each other. The findings and results of this study is matching with the hypothesis of this study such as "Cyber loafing has a significant negative effect on the job performance of employees in HEI" as well as the results is also matching with the idea of Ramayah (2010) according to him, Cyber loafing activities as significant predictors of work inefficiency. In the table 4.5.3 the overall value of Cronbach's alpha is .857 which indicates a high reliability. In the current study the correlation results shows a negative relationship among the variables.

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